

1 **An update on micro- and nanoplastics in foods from plastic food**
2 **contact articles: Protocol for a systematic evidence map**

3 Lisa Zimmermann^a, Birgit Geueke^a, Christoph Schür^b, Martin Wagner^c, Jane Muncke^a

4
5 ^a *Food Packaging Forum Foundation, Staffelstrasse 10, 8045 Zürich, Switzerland*

6 ^b *Eawag, Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology, 8600 Dübendorf, Switzerland*

7 ^c *Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Høgskoleringen 5, 7491 Trondheim,*
8 *Norway*

9
10 Corresponding author: lisa.zimmermann@fp-forum.org;

11 Food Packaging Forum Foundation, Staffelstrasse 10, 8045 Zurich, Switzerland

12
13 DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17151840

14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21 **Keywords**

22 Microplastics, Nanoplastics, Systematic evidence map, Exposure assessment, Food packaging

23 **Abstract**

24 **Background:** The normal and intended use of plastic food packaging and other food contact articles
25 (FCAs) leads to the migration of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) into food and beverages, resulting in
26 human exposure. In 2022, we systematically assessed the state of science on this topic. However, at
27 the time, reliable data on MNP release from FCAs into food were scarce, and since then, research has
28 expanded significantly.

29 **Objectives:** We aim to update our dataset with the latest evidence of MNPs detected in foodstuffs in
30 contact with plastic FCAs. To achieve this, we will systematically map the literature based on a
31 Population, and Outcomes (PO) framework.

32 **Search strategy and eligibility criteria:** We will search Web of Science, PubMed, and Science
33 Direct for combinations of search terms related to FCAs, packaging, foodstuffs/food simulants, plastic
34 particles, and abrasion/release. Cited references from relevant reports will also be included. In a two-
35 step screening process, we will apply predefined eligibility criteria to titles and abstracts of all
36 references, followed by a screening of full texts.

37 **Data extraction:** According to defined data categories, we will collect information on types and
38 characteristics of the FCAs, MNPs, food/food simulant, and the experimental design.

39 **Synthesis and visualization:** Results will be published as a narrative summary, and data in the freely
40 accessible, filterable FCMiNo dashboard.

41 **Author affiliation, ORCID, and Credit statements**

42 Lisa Zimmermann (LZ)

43 <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6801-6859>

44 Food Packaging Forum Foundation, Staffelstrasse 10, 8045 Zürich, Switzerland

45

46 Birgit Geueke (BG)

47 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0749-3982>

48 Food Packaging Forum Foundation, Staffelstrasse 10, 8045 Zürich, Switzerland

49

50 Christoph Schür (CS)

51 <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5865-980X>

52 Eawag, Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology, 8600 Dübendorf, Switzerland

53

54 Martin Wagner (MW)

55 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4402-3234>

56 Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Høgskoleringen 5, 7491 Trondheim,

57 Norway

58

59 Jane Muncke (JM)

60 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6942-0594>

61 Food Packaging Forum Foundation, Staffelstrasse 10, 8045 Zürich, Switzerland

62

63 The authors of this protocol, LZ, BG, CS, MW, and JM, represent the core team developing and
64 implementing the systematic evidence map (SEM). The team combines expertise on experimental
65 micro- and nanoplastics research, databases, and systematic evidence mapping. In addition, all
66 members have been involved in the previous SEM (FCMiNo_v1) as part of the core team or as
67 reviewers of the SEM protocol and have an in-depth understanding of the topic and processes.

68 During the development of this protocol, the core team met regularly to discuss the concept and
69 methodology. LZ and BG refined the literature search as well as the data extraction strategy. LZ wrote
70 the first draft of the protocol. All members of the core team provided constructive input to improve the
71 comprehensibility of the protocol. JM acquired the funding.

72 **1 Introduction**

73 **1.1 Rationale**

74 Micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs) are receiving increasing attention, and concerns about their potential
75 health implications are rising (Ali et al., 2024; Chartres et al., 2024; World Health Organization,
76 2022). MNPs are plastic particles smaller than 1000 μm and 1 μm , respectively. If all sources of
77 human exposure to MNPs were known, then human health could be better protected by addressing the
78 most relevant sources. But the focus is commonly on selected exposure pathways, such as
79 intentionally added MNPs in cosmetics (Han and Kim, 2025), airborne rubber particles from tires
80 (Kreider et al., 2020), and MNPs in food and beverages resulting from environmental contamination
81 (Domenech and Marcos, 2021). Interestingly, the contribution of plastic food packaging and other
82 plastic food contact articles (FCAs), such as storage containers, filling lines, and processing
83 equipment, to the overall human exposure remains largely underappreciated, even though it is likely to
84 be highly relevant (Shruti and Kutralam-Muniasamy, 2024).

85 In mid-2025, we published the Database of MNPs from Food Contact Materials (FCMiNo_v1), which
86 is freely accessible through an interactive [dashboard](#) (Food Packaging Forum Foundation, 2025). In
87 this work, we systematically documented the scientific literature on MNPs found in foodstuffs and
88 food simulants that had contacted plastic FCAs (Zimmermann et al., 2022). This means that the
89 included studies detected MNPs that may have originated from a plastic FCA. Using these data, we
90 critically appraised the studies' quality, eligibility, and relevance for linking MNPs to FCAs.

91 Our assessment demonstrated that the normal and intended use of plastic FCAs can result in the
92 migration, abrasion and release of MNPs into foodstuffs, indicating that FCAs are likely relevant
93 sources for human exposure. However, we also identified a scarcity of reliable and relevant studies at
94 the time. In many cases, overall study quality was low, methods and data reporting were not suitable
95 for identifying the FCAs and MNP polymer type(s), or the design was not relevant to determine the
96 origin of MNPs in food and beverages (Zimmermann et al., 2025). Since December 2022, when we
97 conducted the literature search for FCMiNo_v1, research on MNPs has rapidly expanded, methods
98 have advanced, and study designs have been refined.

99 Therefore, our objective is to update FCMiNo version 1 (FCMiNo_v1) to version 2 (FCMiNo_v2) by
100 including studies published since December 2022 through a SEM exercise, as we outline in this
101 protocol. Based on the mapped data, we will subsequently assess and synthesize the evidence whether
102 the studies detected MNPs that plausibly originated from a plastic FCA or any other source (*e.g.*,
103 environmental contamination). This evidence synthesis is outside of the scope of the current protocol.
104 Building on the learnings from FCMiNo_v1, we aim to improve the search strategy, clarify the
105 eligibility screening criteria, and refine the data extraction process to focus on information valuable to
106 users of the FCMiNo dashboard. Specifically, in data extraction, we will target characteristics of the
107 FCA, food or food simulant, and the MNPs, as well as the experimental design.
108 The selection of the SEM methodology is based on James et al. (2016), which is appropriate given our
109 aims to (i) describe the current state of knowledge, (ii) identify the available evidence, (iii) highlight
110 knowledge gaps for primary research on the topic, and (iv) synthesize findings from a likely
111 heterogeneous body of literature. Ultimately, we aim to update and expand our science-based resource
112 on MNPs in foodstuffs or food simulants in contact with plastic food packaging and other FCAs that
113 will be valuable to researchers, policymakers, influencers, and regulators alike.

114 **1.2 Objectives**

115 The overall objective of our SEM is to provide an overview of the latest scientific literature analyzing
116 MNPs in foodstuffs and food simulants in contact with a plastic or plastic-like FCA or food contact
117 material (FCM). The objective of this protocol is to make our SEM strategy and methods openly
118 available and have them peer-reviewed before we execute them.

119 The specific objectives of the SEM are to:

- 120 • Provide researchers and policymakers with an up-to-date resource that enables exploration of
121 the types of FCAs, foodstuffs, and food simulants studied in connection with MNPs, to identify
122 which studies and experimental setups have shown MNP detection and which have not, and to
123 access information on the underlying primary literature.

- 124 • Collect and code the data needed to subsequently identify studies capable of establishing
125 causality between MNPs detected in foodstuff and plastic or plastic-like FCA or FCM as their
126 source, *i.e.*, studies with a spatial or kinetic study design.

127 **1.3 Definitions**

128 Here, we provide a list of terms and definitions used in our SEM and throughout this protocol.

129 **Food:** Solid or liquid non-medicinal product intended for human consumption by any age group,
130 including beverages and ingredients (like salt).

131 **Food contact articles (FCAs):** Products or items that intentionally come into contact with food, such
132 as packaging, storage containers, tableware, cooking utensils, tubes, and processing equipment.

133 **Food contact materials (FCMs):** Any material that is intended for use in the manufacture of an FCA
134 and that is typically in direct contact with food (*e.g.*, the inner plastic lining of a metal can). Materials
135 that are not in direct contact with the food but may be a source of chemicals migrating into food (*e.g.*,
136 printing inks) are also considered FCMs.

137 **Food simulant:** A liquid or solid substance or mixture that is chemically well-defined and used in
138 extraction or migration experiments. Food simulants may include those defined in European Union
139 (EU) or United States (US) regulations (EU, 2011; Food and Drug Administration, 2007).

140 **Mesoplastics:** Plastic particles of any shape and with a size between 1 and <10 mm following the
141 definition of Harmann et al. (2019).

142 **Microplastics (MPs):** Plastic particles of any shape and with a size between 1 and <1000 μm
143 following the ISO/TR21960:2020 (ISO, 2020).

144 **Migration:** Transfer of a chemical or a mixture of chemicals from an FCM or FCA into food or food
145 simulant under realistic, intended use, and foreseeable conditions. We also include the migration of a
146 small-sized solids (*e.g.*, micro- or nanoplastics) under that definition, which is traditionally not
147 covered but should be considered. Particle migration includes release and abrasion (*i.e.*, the process of

148 MNPs splitting off a plastic FCM or FCA). The migration of a chemical, chemical mixture, or small-
149 sized solid into food may result in human exposure through food consumption.

150 **Migration study:** Experimental setup measuring the migration of a chemical or particle from an
151 FCM/FCA into food or food simulant.

152 **Nanoplastics (NPs):** Plastic particles of any shape and with a size of <1 µm following the
153 ISO/TR21960:2020 (ISO, 2020).

154 **Non-intentionally added substance (NIAS):** Chemicals present in the final article without having a
155 technical function. NIAS include impurities in the starting substances for FCM manufacture,
156 contaminants, side products (oligomers) of processing, and breakdown products.

157 **Intended use of food packaging:** Handling of food packaging as suggested (*i.e.*, intended) by the
158 packaging manufacturer during the food packaging process, transportation, storage, and consumption.

159 **Normal use of food packaging:** Handling of food packaging as perceived appropriate (*i.e.*, normal)
160 by the person handling the packaging.

161 **Particle:** A small-sized solid form suspended in a medium of interest (*e.g.*, food, food simulant) <10
162 mm.

163 **Plastic:** “Materials that contain as an essential ingredient one or more organic macromolecules of
164 large molecular mass, are solid in the finished state, and at some stage in their manufacture or
165 processing can be shaped by flow,” according to ISO 472:2021 (ISO, 2013).

166 **Plastic-like materials:** Organic synthetic materials that are polymerized, including elastomers (*e.g.*,
167 rubbers), adhesives, as well as polymeric coatings, binders, pigments, and varnishes. Silicones are also
168 considered under this category. These are inorganic synthetic polymers with an inorganic polysiloxane
169 backbone and with organic units added as side chains.

170 **2 Methods**

171 We developed this protocol using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-
172 analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) guideline according to the PRISMA-P 2015 checklist and the
173 associated elaboration and explanation (Shamseer et al., 2015). Learnings from our previous SEM
174 (FCMiNo_v1) on the topic helped with the planning, designing, and writing of the protocol for this
175 SEM (FCMiNo_v2).

176 **2.1 Research question**

177 Our research question is: What is the current state of knowledge regarding MNPs detected in
178 foodstuffs and food simulants that contacted a plastic or plastic-like FCM or FCA?

179 To structure the research question of our SEM, the eligibility criteria, and the data extraction
180 categories, we will apply the Population, Outcome framework (PO) (James et al., 2016):

- 181 • Population: Food or food simulant
- 182 • Outcome: Presence of MNP & Originating from an FCA

183 **2.2 Eligibility criteria**

184 To identify the eligible studies during the title and abstract screening and during full text screening, we
185 used the PO framework to develop and structure criteria for inclusion and exclusion. We will include
186 studies that analyze food or food simulant (Population) in contact with a plastic or plastic-like FCM or
187 FCA for the presence of plastic particles smaller than 10 mm, including MNPs (Outcome). Studies
188 examining plastic particles on the inner surface of an FCA made of plastic or a plastic-like material we
189 also deem to be eligible (Table 1).

190 **Table 1.** Eligibility criteria for outcomes of PO.

PO element	Description	Eligibility criteria	Include	Exclude
Population	Food or food simulant	Analyzed sample is food/food simulant/surface of plastic FCA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analysis of all types of foods and beverages - Analysis of animal (<i>e.g.</i>, fish, seafood) which can serve as food (<i>e.g.</i>, referred to as “edible”, “consumed by humans”) - Analysis of foodstuffs known or indicated to be consumed by tribal or indigenous populations (<i>e.g.</i>, whales) - Analysis of the inside air or inner surface of an FCA - Analysis of all types of food simulants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plastic particle is not analyzed in food/food simulant but elsewhere - Analysis of animal not intended for consumption (<i>e.g.</i>, fish that is not edible, fish & seafood caught for the purpose of monitoring environmental contamination, exposure studies that analyze MNP effects) - Analysis of foodstuff or food simulant to which MNPs were added (‘spiked’) prior to analysis (<i>e.g.</i>, to test the recovery of applied methods to purify and analyze MNPs)
Outcome	MNP	Plastic particle < 10 mm* (<i>i.e.</i> , MNP) is analyzed in sample	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study intends to analyze MNPs and states detect or not detect of plastic particles < 10 mm - Particle size is not given but text refers to “microplastics”, “nanoplastic” and/or “plastic particle” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study intends to only analyze plastic particle > 10 mm - If “particles” are reported but it is not conclusively described that they are made of plastic (<i>e.g.</i>, in the case of “nanoparticle”)
	Plastic FCM/FCA	At least one part of the FCM or FCA in contact with the sample is reported or assumed** to be made of plastic and/or plastic-like material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FCM/FCA is reported to be made of a plastic and/or plastic-like material - FCM/FCA that are assumed to include a plastic/plastic-like material based on the typical composition of the reported food packaging. These include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Glass bottles and jars since they likely have a plastic or plastic-coated metal closure with a gasket • Cans, beverage cartons (<i>i.e.</i>, multilayer materials), and paper/cardboard cups since they likely have an inner plastic or plastic-like film or coating • Cardboard boxes, containers, or paper wraps in contact with fatty or moist food (<i>e.g.</i>, pizza boxes, wraps around cheese, cold cuts) - Tap/drinking water, since distribution pipes or storage containers might be made of plastic, which 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Foods and beverages that are <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • not mentioned to be packaged AND • not assumed to be packaged inevitably, AND • not assumed to contact plastic during processing, distribution, or storage (<i>i.e.</i>, tap/drinking water). - Packaging in parenteral nutrition (<i>e.g.</i>, infusion bags), experimental materials not yet on the market (<i>e.g.</i>, active and intelligent material)

			<p>means that the studied foodstuff comes into contact with plastic during distribution or storage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compostable plastic trash bags, since they might not only be used for waste disposal but also to transport/store food - If no packaging is reported but the foodstuff is assumed to be packaged inevitably (<i>e.g.</i>, beer, soda, honey, salt), and this packaging is known or assumed to have a plastic component, based on expert judgement 	
--	--	--	--	--

191 *Besides nanoplastics (<1 µm) and microplastics (1 to <1000 µm), we also consider mesoplastics to capture particles of 1–10 mm, which can sometimes be included under the
192 term “microplastics”.

193 ** We include studies on FCMs/FCAs that are not reported but only assumed to include a plastic/plastic-like material in the eligibility screening because plastic components of an
194 FCM/FCA may not be reported in a study. For example, metal cans typically contain a plastic-like inner coating that could be a source of MNPs, but this detail may not be
195 mentioned in a study.

196 Note: If the title and abstract lack the information needed to judge inclusion or exclusion, we include the study at the title and abstract level. For instance, if the title and abstract
197 do not indicate whether the studied food was packaged at some stage, or whether that packaging included plastic.

198 **2.3 Information sources**

199 To identify relevant indexed scientific literature, we will conduct systematic searches in the following
200 bibliographic databases: PubMed, Web of Science Core Collection (WoS) all editions, and
201 ScienceDirect.

202 In addition, we have identified relevant reports addressing MNPs in foodstuffs and published by
203 authoritative sources (intergovernmental or governmental agencies) after December 14, 2022 (the date
204 of the FCMiNo_v1 literature search). These reports cite a broad range of primary scientific studies,
205 which we will subject to eligibility screening. We will only screen cited studies published after
206 December 14, 2022. To date, we have identified the following reports for inclusion in our SEM.
207 However, if additional relevant reports are published while we are conducting our SEM, we may
208 consider adding them as well:

- 209 • European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment and University of the West of
210 England (UWE). Science Communication Unit. 2023. *Nanoplastics – State of knowledge
211 and environmental and human health impacts*. Publications Office of the European Union.
212 <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/632649>
- 213 • Committee on Toxicity of Chemicals in Food, Consumer Products and the Environment,
214 2024. *Sub-statement on the potential risk(s) from exposure to microplastics: Inhalation
215 route: Microplastics - Inhalation route – Background*. [Report COT/2024/01](https://www.food.gov.uk/news/news-detail/1212). London. 55 pp.
- 216 • Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). Garrido Gamarro, E. &
217 Costanzo, V. 2022. *Microplastics in food commodities – A food safety review on human
218 exposure through dietary sources*. Food Safety and Quality Series No. 18. Rome,
219 FAO. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc2392en>
- 220 • FAO. 2023. *The impact of microplastics on the gut microbiome and health – A food safety
221 perspective*. Food Safety and Quality Series, No. 21. Rome.
222 <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc5294en>
- 223 • United Nations Environment Program (UNEP). 2023. *Turning off the Tap: How the world
224 can end plastic pollution and create a circular economy*. Chapter *Prevent microplastics at*

225 *their source*. Nairobi. [https://www.unep.org/resources/turning-off-tap-end-plastic-pollution-](https://www.unep.org/resources/turning-off-tap-end-plastic-pollution-create-circular-economy)
226 [create-circular-economy](https://www.unep.org/resources/turning-off-tap-end-plastic-pollution-create-circular-economy)

- 227 • European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). 2025. Literature review on micro- and nanoplastic
228 release from food contact materials during their use. EFSA Journal A.
229 <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.2903/sp.efsa.2025.EN-9733>

230 **2.4 Search strategy**

231 **2.4.1 Search string development**

232 In FCMiNo_v1, we identified 5979 potentially relevant studies, of which we extracted data for only
233 1.72% (103 studies; Zimmermann et al., 2025). To develop a more targeted search string for WoS and
234 PubMed, we used these 103 studies as a benchmark. As a first approach, we constructed a search
235 string based on the titles of the benchmark studies. Through an iterative process, we tested and refined
236 the string for each database, evaluating its specificity and sensitivity. In an alternative approach to
237 developing a search string, we added certain search terms (*e.g.*, types of food and beverages) and
238 removed others from the FCMiNo_v1 search string. Finally, we tested different combinations of the
239 search groups developed in the two approaches and selected the combination that reduces the
240 screening burden compared to FCMiNo_v1 while still identifying (highly) relevant studies (Table 2).
241 ScienceDirect limits the number of search terms that can be used, allowing, for example, a maximum
242 of eight terms in full-text searches. As a result, we developed a simplified version of the search string
243 and optimized it separately for this database. The Supplementary Information includes details on the
244 search string development and optimization.

245 Furthermore, we assessed whether our search approach identified five recently published seed studies
246 on the topic, that is, studies we identified as potentially relevant before starting the pilot searches and
247 published after we conducted the literature searches for FCMiNo_v1 (*i.e.*, December 14, 2022):

- 248 • Rongyi Gong et al. (2023). Analysis of microplastics release from rice package in combination
249 with machine learning and hyperspectral imaging technique. Food Packaging and Shelf Life. 39,
250 101152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fpsl.2023.101152>.

- 251 • Kazi Albab Hussain et al. (2023). Assessing the Release of Microplastics and Nanoplastics from
252 Plastic Containers and Reusable Food Pouches: Implications for Human Health. *Environmental*
253 *Science & Technology* 2023 57 (26), 9782-9792.
254 <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.est.3c01942>
- 255 • Xin Guo et al. (2024). Migration testing of microplastics from selected water and food
256 containers by Raman microscopy. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*. 462, 132798.
257 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2023.132798>.
- 258 • Huier Chen et al. (2023) Release of microplastics from disposable cups in daily use. *Science of*
259 *The Total Environment*. 854, 158606. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158606>
- 260 • Jia-Ling Hua et al. (2022). Analysis of microplastics released from plastic take-out food
261 containers based on thermal properties and morphology study. *Food Additives & Contaminants:*
262 *Part A*. 40(2), 305–318. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19440049.2022.2157894>

263 All five additional seed studies were retrieved from at least two of the three databases searched.

264 **2.4.2 Search string implementation**

265 To identify the relevant scientific literature in PubMed and WoS, we will apply six groups of search
266 terms covering plastic particles (Group 1), food/food simulant (2), packaging (3), FCA (4), and the
267 process of plastic particle release (5 and 6; Table 2). We will connect terms within one group with the
268 Boolean operator ‘OR’.

269 Groups 1 to 4 correspond to those of our previous search with minor modifications. Specifically, we
270 removed polymer types from Group 1 while adding further foodstuff and FCA types to Groups 2 and
271 4, respectively. For a study to be retrieved, the search string requires either one term from each of
272 Groups 1 and 2 plus at least one term from Groups 3 or 4, or one term from each of Groups 5 and 6
273 (Table 2).

274 With the inclusion of Groups 5 and 6, we intended to more precisely target studies focusing on the
275 migration process, *i.e.*, those in which nano- or microplastics and a migration-related term appear
276 within 10 words of each other (Group 5), and where some form of packaging is described (Group 6).

277 As advanced search functionalities differ between PubMed and Web of Science, we adapted individual
 278 terms and search settings accordingly for each database. For instance, in PubMed, we will not use
 279 wildcards for the terms tea, nut, bag, cup, cap, lid, and jar since terms must have four or more
 280 characters before the first wildcard.

281 **Table 2.** Search terms PubMed and WoS grouped by topic.

Search number	Topic group	Search terms
1	Particle	nanoplastic* OR "nano plastic*" OR "nano-sized plastic*" OR "nano sized plastic*" OR microplastic* OR "micro plastic*" OR "micro-sized plastic*" OR "micro sized plastic*" OR "plastic particle*" OR "plastic fragment*" OR "plastic sphere*" OR "plastic bead*" OR "plastic pellet*" OR "plastic foam*" OR "synthetic particle*" OR "plastic microparticle*" OR "plastic nanoparticle"
2	Food/food simulant	food* OR drink* OR beverage* OR foodstuff* OR nutrition OR "mineral water*" OR "bottled water*" OR "bottled drinking water*" OR "tap water*" OR "soda*" OR "beer*" OR "wine*" OR "tea*" OR "coffee*" OR "milk*" OR "seafood*" OR "fish" OR "mollusc*" OR mollusk* OR mussel* OR sardine* OR bivalve* OR meat* OR chicken* OR rice OR pasta OR noodle* OR flour* OR bread* OR sandwich* OR soup* OR stew* OR chocolate* OR candy OR sugar* OR honey OR salt* OR fruit* OR vegetable* OR salad* OR cereal* OR nut* OR cream* OR cake* OR cheese OR egg OR pizza OR pepper OR spice* OR oil OR vinegar OR yogurt OR tofu OR seed*
3	Packaging	packaging OR packing OR packaged OR canned
4	FCA (including terms related to food processing and transport)	bottle* OR container* OR "shrink film*" OR foil* OR wrap* OR wrapping* OR bag* OR plate* OR glass OR cutlery OR cup* OR gasket* OR closure* OR cap* OR lid* OR jar* OR tableware* OR "food container*" OR "frying pan*" OR cookware OR "food processing equipment*" OR pipe* OR hose* OR "storage tank*" OR valve* OR pump* OR barrel* OR food transport equipment* OR kettle* OR chopping board*
5	Particle NEAR process/generic foodstuff	microplastic* NEAR/10 migration OR microplastic* NEAR/10 release OR microplastic* NEAR/10 contamination OR microplastic* NEAR/10 pollution Or microplastic* NEAR/10 presence OR microplastic* NEAR/10 abrasion OR microplastic* NEAR/10 food* OR microplastic* NEAR/10 beverage* OR microplastic* NEAR/10 drink* OR microplastic* NEAR/10 water OR nanoplastic* NEAR/10 migration OR nanoplastic* NEAR/10 release OR nanoplastic* NEAR/10 contamination OR nanoplastic* NEAR/10 pollution OR nanoplastic* NEAR/10 presence OR nanoplastic* NEAR/10 abrasion OR nanoplastic* NEAR/10 food* OR nanoplastic* NEAR/10 beverage* OR nanoplastic* NEAR/10 drink* OR nanoplastic* NEAR/10 water
6	Packaging including bottle	packaging OR bottle* OR canned OR packaged
Combined as		((#1 AND #2 AND (#3 OR #4)) OR (#5 AND #6))

282 The asterisk (*) substitutes for 0 or more characters in a term.

283 The use of double quotes ("xxx") prevents the term from undergoing the database's automatic term mapping.
284 Accordingly, citations that are indexed to MeSH terms in PubMed will not be shown.
285 The use of NEAR/10 finds records where the terms joined by the operator are within 10 words of each other.

286

287 As ScienceDirect only allows entering a limited number of search terms (*e.g.*, eight in the full text
288 search), an alternative approach is needed. Accordingly, we will search the full text for the string
289 (packaging OR packaged OR packing OR canned OR bottled) and the title, abstract, or author-
290 specified keywords for ((food OR beverage OR drink OR "drinking water" OR "mineral water" OR
291 "bottled water") AND (microplastic OR nanoplastic OR "plastic particle")).

292 We will limit our searches to original research articles in English published after December 14, 2022
293 (when we conducted the FCMiNo_v1 search) with full text available and excluding reviews, book
294 chapters, dissertations, conference abstracts, presentations, and other editorials.

295 **2.5 Study selection**

296 To remove duplicate studies identified during the literature search, we will first use the reference
297 manager Citavi 7.0, followed by the deduplication function in SWIFT-Active Screener (Howard et al.,
298 2020). Next, the core team will screen the studies in SWIFT-Active Screener for eligibility, first
299 evaluating titles and abstracts, followed by the full texts. We will exclude studies that do not meet the
300 PO inclusion criteria.

301 Title and abstract screening will be actively supported by SWIFT-Active Screener, which uses
302 relevant studies as training data to iteratively prioritize studies most likely to be eligible for further
303 manual review. We will set a 95% recall level, indicating the proportion of eligible studies expected to
304 be included based on the prediction model.

305 To ensure consistency, two core team members will screen the first 10% of titles and abstracts in
306 parallel. This step will verify whether both reviewers independently reach the same conclusions;
307 discrepancies will help to further refine the eligibility criteria. A continuously updated guidance
308 document will support decision-making during the screening process. SWIFT-Active Screener tracks
309 potential inconsistencies, which we will discuss in regular core team meetings and resolve by

310 consensus. After we have screened the initial 10% of studies in parallel, we will assess the inter-
 311 reviewer reliability score (IRR) by means of the Cohen's kappa score. If the score is above 0.6
 312 (indicating acceptable/moderate agreement (Hanegraaf et al., 2024)), a single reviewer will proceed
 313 with screening. If the score is below 0.6, we will screen another 10% of studies in parallel before
 314 reassessing the IRR. We will repeat this process until the IRR exceeds the 0.6 threshold or screening is
 315 concluded.

316 All studies we deemed eligible in the title and abstract screening will undergo manual full-text
 317 screening. As with title and abstract screening, we will screen 10% of the studies in parallel, and we
 318 will resolve any disagreements using the same consensus-based approach.

319 Using a PRISMA flow diagram, we will illustrate the total number of studies found in the literature
 320 searches, the number of included/excluded ones at the two different screening levels, and the reasons
 321 for exclusion at full-text level (Figure 1).

322

323
 324 **Figure 1.** Planned workflow based on the PRISM flow diagram, indicating the number (N) of included and
 325 excluded studies after each step.

326

327 2.6 Data extraction

328 2.6.1 Software

329 The core team will extract data from all studies included after full-text screening using the custom
330 software tool SciExtract (Geueke et al., 2023). SciExtract enables systematic and semi-automated data
331 selection and storage. For example, it allows the definition of data categories to be extracted (*e.g.*,
332 FCA type) along with relevant key terms (*e.g.*, bottle, cup) presented as drop-down menus. In some
333 cases, we may also enter data as free text or numerical values in a pre-coded format. Depending on the
334 category, users can select one or several answers. All but one category are mandatory for extraction.
335 The generated results can be exported and used in other software tools for further analysis.

336 2.6.2 Code book

337 We will extract details on the FCA, food & food simulants, MNPs, and methods & experimental
338 design (Table 3). Compared to FCMiNo_v1, we will extract only a subset of the data as done before.
339 In version 1, our goal was to obtain an overview of the type and amount of data available on the topic.
340 This led to comprehensive data extraction, including from many studies that were irrelevant or
341 unreliable. Building on this overview and lessons learned, we now adapt our approach to focus on
342 extracting data most useful for the scientific and regulatory community and suitable for display in an
343 accessible manner. Furthermore, the extracted data will enable us to easily identify the studies that will
344 be subject to evidence synthesis in a subsequent step, which is outside the scope of this protocol. In
345 that second step, we will extract additional data.

346 **Table 3.** Data reported based on pre-coded answer choices.

	Data category	Answer choices
Bibliographic information	Author	*free text* (automated)
	Title	*free text* (automated)
	Year of publication	*free text* (automated)
	URL	*free text* (automated)
	Journal	*free text* (automated)
	Volume	*free text* (automated)
	Issues	*free text* (automated)
	Pages	*free text* (automated)
	Abstract	*free text* (automated)
	DOI	*free text* (automated)
FCA	(Sample Id)	*free text*

	Country of sampling	unknown "free text"
	Single or repeat use	single-use repeat use unclear/unknown
	FCA 1 - usage type	bottle cup cutlery bag tray wrapping jar can beverage carton tea bag bottle cap baby bottle & feeding accessory other container packaged but not specified food delivery system food processing & transport equipment *free text*
	FCA 1 – material type(s)	PE PS PP PET rPET PVC PU PC PA PLA cellulose silicone melamine "plastic" but polymer type not indicated assumed to be made of plastic glass metal paper & board multi-material other material unclear/unknown *free text*
	(FCA 2 - usage type)	lid/cap lining/coating gasket baby bottle & feeding accessory food processing & transport equipment other accessory unclear/unknown *free text*
	(FCA 2 - polymer type)	PE PS PP PET rPET PVC PU PC PA

		PLA cellulose silicone melamine "plastic" but polymer type not indicated assumed to be made of plastics unclear/unknown *free text*
	Sample includes different brands	yes no
	FCA modified from normal use*	yes no
	(If FCA modified =“yes”, specify*)	“free text”
Methods & Experimental design	Experimental series**	yes no
	MNP detection method(s)	light microscopy fluorescence microscopy confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) scanning electron microscopy (SEM) transmission electron microscopy (TEM) electrochemical strain microscopy (ESM) atomic force microscopy (AFM) electron microscopy–energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EM–EDX) scanning transmission X-ray microscopy (STXM) scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry (SEM-EDX) infrared spectroscopy and scanning electron microscopy (IR-SEM) infrared absorption spectroscopy atomic force microscopy-based infrared spectroscopy (AFM-IR) nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy Raman spectroscopy μ -Raman Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) μ -FTIR attenuated total reflectance (ATR)-FTIR X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) optical-photothermal infrared (O-PTIR) spectroscopy energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) laser direct infrared (LDIR) spectroscopy LDIR imaging particle tracking analysis (PTA) dynamic image particle analysis (DIPA) single particle extinction and scattering (SPES) nanoparticles tracking analysis (NTA) dynamic light scattering (DLS) flow cytometry flow field fractionation (FFF) laser diffraction method

		pyrolysis gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (Pyr-GC/MS) microwave-assisted extraction Pyr-GC/MS thermal desorption (TD)-GC/MS thermal extraction-desorption (TED)-GC-MS liquid chromatography-high resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) hydrodynamic chromatography (HDC) with UV detection coupled plasma mass spectrometry (spICP-MS) coupled plasma mass spectrometry (CP-MS) thermogravimetric analysis with differential scanning calorimetry (TGA-DSC) unknown/unclear *free text* (text)
Food/food simulant	medium MNP was analyzed in	solid foodstuff liquid foodstuff food simulant direct FCA surface analysis unknown/unclear
	type of food/food simulant	*free text* (text) unclear/unknown
MNP	detected	yes no
	size – category(s)	NP (<1 µm) MP (1 - 1000 µm) mesoplastics (1 - 10 mm) unclear/unknown
	polymer type(s)	PE PS PP PET rPET PVC PU PC PA PLA cellulose silicone melamine other plastic "plastic" but polymer type not indicated assumed to be made of plastic not applicable unclear/unknown *free text* (text)

347 The use of the plural form (“s”) in a category name indicates that multiple answers may be selected.

348 Data not mandatory to be extracted are indicated in brackets.

349 *Examples of modifications include but are not limited to FCA washed before use, FCA cut, packaging content
 350 removed, and only a piece of the FCA was analyzed.

351 **Experimental series refers to study designs that allow for establishing causality between the MNPs and a

352 plastic FCA. A causal relationship can be established with a kinetic design, where several MNP measurements

353 are taken over time, at increasing temperatures or UV exposure, or different levels of (mechanical) stress. Re-use
 354 falls under kinetic design. Here, different levels of mechanical stress (e.g., dishwashing) are applied to the FCA
 355 in between each use. Alternatively, the design can be spatial, where MNPs are measured in solid foodstuffs, at
 356 the food surface close to the FCA and further inside.

357
 358 We will structure the extracted information as database entries. We will create a single database entry
 359 for all sample and technical replicates of an FCA (defined by one usage type, one material/polymer
 360 type, and one combination of FCA 1 and 2) applied to a specific food/food simulant. Also, in case of a
 361 spatial or kinetic study design where several MNP measurements are taken at different times,
 362 temperatures, UV exposure, or stress levels, we will create one database entry. As a result, a single
 363 study can result in one or several database entries (see Table 4). This definition of a database entry
 364 differs from FCMiNo_v1.

365 **Table 4.** Examples demonstrating cases under which one or more database entries are created.

FCA and experimental setup	Number of database entries	Explanation
Three replicates of a PE container from the same brand in contact with soup.	1	One type of FCA, one type of food/food simulant. Replicates are combined in one entry.
One PE container from three different brands, each in contact with soup.	1	One type of FCA, one type of food/food simulant. A separate data category allows for specifying that “sample includes different brands.”
Two PP and one PE containers in contact with soup.	2	One entry per material type: PP, PE.
Two PP and one PE containers, each in contact with soup and in contact with water.	4	One entry for each combination of material and food/food simulant type: PP – soup, PP – water, PE – soup, PE – water.
Three PE containers in contact with soup for 20, 40, and 60 min.	1	One type of FCA was subjected to a time-dependent experimental series.
Three PE containers in contact with soup for 20, 40, and 60 min at room temperature, and 80 °C each.	1	One type of FCA was subjected to a time- and temperature-dependent experimental series.

366

367 **2.6.4 Processes to ensure consistent, unbiased data extraction**

368 To test the data extraction process and ensure consistency in answer selection, two team members will
 369 independently extract the data of 10% of the studies. We will compare the results, discuss any
 370 discrepancies, and resolve them either bilaterally or with input from a third team member. Based on
 371 this pilot phase, we may refine the data extraction process and answer options. Importantly, we will
 372 carefully review any adaptations to ensure compatibility with existing data, including data from

373 FCMiNo_v1. A previously prepared guidance document supports team members in selecting the most
374 appropriate answer(s) for each category. We will continuously update this document throughout the
375 testing and data extraction. If, within the first 10% of double-extracted data, team members disagree
376 on more than 10% of the answer choices, two team members will independently extract an additional
377 10% of studies before reassessing discrepancies. We will repeat this process until fewer than 10% of
378 answer choices differ between team members. A single team member will then process the remaining
379 studies. In cases of uncertainty regarding one or more categories, the team member will consult with
380 another team member. We may exclude studies during data extraction if new information warrants a
381 revision of the initial eligibility decision. A second team member must review and agree upon such
382 decisions.

383 **2.7 Data presentation/accessibility and reporting**

384 We will use the extracted data to update the FCMiNo database from version 1 to version 2. Since we
385 changed the definition of what we consider one sample (*i.e.*, one database entry) and reduced the
386 number of data categories extracted when moving from version 1 to version 2, the update will be
387 accompanied by a change in the number of database entries and a slight restructuring of the current
388 FCMiNo database. During restructuring, we will include an option to filter FCA reported to contain
389 plastic versus FCA assumed to contain plastic based on expert judgement (*e.g.*, metal cans, which
390 typically have an inner plastic lining).

391 The database is freely accessible via the interactive [FCMiNo dashboard](#) built in Power BI, which
392 visualizes the data using bar graphs. Structured text with tick boxes allows for easy selection and
393 highlighting of specific data, such as polymer types of FCAs or MNPs. When a dataset is filtered, only
394 the corresponding underlying references are displayed. With the revision of our dashboard, we will
395 ensure to include all data extracted in version 2, guaranteeing free accessibility to all data for all users.
396 The complete and filtered dataset, as well as the references, cannot be downloaded directly from the
397 dashboard. However, we will make the data available as a single, machine-readable file upon request.
398 The prerequisite is that the external user's intended use of the dataset is non-commercial and in the
399 interest of common good, as well as that the data are correctly referenced as originating from the

400 FCMiNo database, citing the related publication. We will submit a manuscript to a peer-reviewed
401 scientific journal in which we summarize our methodology, as well as present and discuss our results.
402 We will make both the manuscript and the database openly available to ensure transparency and
403 accessibility. Also, in the future, we plan to regularly update the FCMiNo database to include the
404 latest scientific findings.

405 **2.8 Data analysis**

406 After completing the descriptive systematic evidence mapping outlined in this protocol, we will use
407 the coded data to perform an evidence synthesis, which lies outside the scope of this protocol. This
408 synthesis will allow us to assess whether the MNPs detected in food or food simulant could plausibly
409 have originated from an FCA, rather than from another source such as environmental contamination.

410 While we will define the exact approach of the synthesis once the SEM is completed, the evaluation of
411 a study's quality and reliability will be part of it.

412 Taken together, FCMiNo_v2 will provide an up-to-date knowledge base on MNPs found in foods,
413 beverages, and food simulants in contact with plastic FCAs. It further lays the foundation for
414 subsequent evidence assessments of MNPs generated through the normal and intended use of plastic
415 FCAs, as well as an in-depth exploration of MNP quantities and sizes.

416 **Abbreviations**

FCA	Food contact article
FCM	Food contact material
FCMiNo	Database of MNPs from Food Contact Materials
IAS	Intentionally added substances
MNP	Micro- and nanoplastics
MP	Microplastic
NIAS	Non-intentionally added substances
NP	Nanoplastic
POS	Population, outcome, study design
SEM	Systematic evidence map

417

418 **Funding**

419 This work is funded by the Food Packaging Forum's (FPF) own resources from unrestricted
420 donations. All FPF funding sources are listed at [https://www.foodpackagingforum.org/about-](https://www.foodpackagingforum.org/about-us/funding)
421 [us/funding](https://www.foodpackagingforum.org/about-us/funding).

422 **Competing Interests**

423 The authors were not restricted in any way in conceptualizing this study, writing the protocol, and
424 executing it. MW is an unremunerated member of the Scientific Advisory Board of FPF.

425 **ORCID**

426 Lisa Zimmermann: 0000-0001-6801-6859

427 Birgit Geueke: 0000-0002-0749-3982

428 Jane Muncke: 0000-0002-6942-0594

429 Christoph Schür: 0000-0001-5865-980X

430 Martin Wagner: 0000-0002-4402-3234

431 **3 References**

- 432 Ali, N., Katsouli, J., Marczylo, E.L., Gant, T.W., Wright, S., La Bernardino de Serna, J., 2024. The
433 potential impacts of micro-and-nano plastics on various organ systems in humans. *EBioMedicine*
434 99, 104901. doi:10.1016/j.ebiom.2023.104901.
- 435 Chartres, N., Cooper, C.B., Bland, G., Pelch, K.E., Gandhi, S.A., BakenRa, A., Woodruff, T.J., 2024.
436 Effects of Microplastic Exposure on Human Digestive, Reproductive, and Respiratory Health: A
437 Rapid Systematic Review. *Environmental Science & Technology* 58 (52), 22843–22864.
438 doi:10.1021/acs.est.3c09524.
- 439 Domenech, J., Marcos, R., 2021. Pathways of human exposure to microplastics, and estimation of the
440 total burden. *Current Opinion in Food Science* 39, 144–151. doi:10.1016/j.cofs.2021.01.004.
- 441 EU, 2011. Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended
442 to come into contact with food, 89 pp.
- 443 Food and Drug Administration, 2007. Guidance for Industry: Preparation of Premarket Submissions
444 for Food Contact Substances (Chemistry recommendations). [https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-](https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/guidance-industry-preparation-premarket-submissions-food-contact-substances-chemistry)
445 [information/search-fda-guidance-documents/guidance-industry-preparation-premarket-](https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/guidance-industry-preparation-premarket-submissions-food-contact-substances-chemistry)
446 [submissions-food-contact-substances-chemistry](https://www.fda.gov/regulatory-information/search-fda-guidance-documents/guidance-industry-preparation-premarket-submissions-food-contact-substances-chemistry) (retrieved 25.07.22).
- 447 Food Packaging Forum Foundation (2025) “FCMiNo Database.”
448 <https://foodpackagingforum.org/mino>
- 449 Geueke, B., Groh, K.J., Maffini, M.V., Martin, O.V., Boucher, J.M., Chiang, Y.-T., Gwosdz, F., Jieh,
450 P., Kassotis, C.D., Łańska, P., Myers, J.P., Odermatt, A., Parkinson, L.V., Schreier, V.N., Srebny,
451 V., Zimmermann, L., Scheringer, M., Muncke, J., 2023. Systematic evidence on migrating and
452 extractable food contact chemicals: Most chemicals detected in food contact materials are not
453 listed for use. *Critical reviews in food science and nutrition* 63 (28), 9425–9435.
454 doi:10.1080/10408398.2022.2067828.
- 455 Han, J.H., Kim, H.S., 2025. Microplastics in Cosmetics: Emerging Risks for Skin Health and the
456 Environment. *Cosmetics* 12 (4), 171. doi:10.3390/cosmetics12040171.
- 457 Hanegraaf, P., Wondimu, A., Mosselman, J.J., Jong, R. de, Abogunrin, S., Queiros, L., Lane, M.,
458 Postma, M.J., Boersma, C., van der Schans, J., 2024. Inter-reviewer reliability of human literature

459 reviewing and implications for the introduction of machine-assisted systematic reviews: a mixed-
460 methods review. *BMJ Open* 14 (3), e076912. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2023-076912.

461 Hartmann, N., Hüffer, T., Thompson, R.C., Hassellöv, M., Verschoor, A., Daugaard, A.E., Rist, S.,
462 Karlsson, T.M., Brennholt, N., Cole, M., Herrling, M.P., Heß, M., Ivleva, N.P., Lusher, A.L.,
463 Wagner, M., 2019. Are we speaking the same language? Recommendations for a definition and
464 categorization framework for plastic debris. *Environmental Science & Technology* 53 (3), 1039–
465 1047. doi:10.1021/acs.est.8b05297.

466 Howard, B.E., Phillips, J., Tandon, A., Maharana, A., Elmore, R., Mav, D., Sedykh, A., Thayer, K.,
467 Merrick, B.A., Walker, V., Rooney, A., Shah, R.R., 2020. SWIFT-Active Screener: Accelerated
468 document screening through active learning and integrated recall estimation. *Environment*
469 *International* 138, 105623. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2020.105623.

470 ISO, 2013. ISO 472:2013, *Plastics - Vocabulary ISO 472:2013*. International Organization for
471 Standardization. <https://www.iso.org/standard/44102.html> (retrieved 11.09.25).

472 ISO, 2020. ISO/TR 21960:2020: *Plastics — Environmental aspects — State of knowledge and*
473 *methodologies*, 41 pp.

474 James, K.L., Randall, N.P., Haddaway, N.R., 2016. A methodology for systematic mapping in
475 environmental sciences. *Environ Evid* 5 (1). doi:10.1186/s13750-016-0059-6.

476 Kreider, M.L., Unice, K.M., Panko, J.M., 2020. Human health risk assessment of Tire and Road Wear
477 Particles (TRWP) in air. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal* 26
478 (10), 2567–2585. doi:10.1080/10807039.2019.1674633.

479 Pang, L., Lin, Q., Zhao, S., Zheng, H., Li, C., Zhang, J., Sun, C., Chen, L., Li, F., 2023. Data quality
480 assessment for studies investigating microplastics and nanoplastics in food products: Are current
481 data reliable? *Frontiers of Environmental Science & Engineering* 17 (8). doi:10.1007/s11783-023-
482 1694-0.

483 Shamseer, L., Moher, D., Clarke, M., Ghersi, D., Liberati, A., Petticrew, M., Shekelle, P., Stewart,
484 L.A., 2015. Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols
485 (PRISMA-P) 2015: elaboration and explanation. *BMJ (Clinical research ed.)* 350, g7647.
486 doi:10.1136/bmj.g7647.

487 Shruti, V.C., Kutralam-Muniasamy, G., 2024. Migration testing of microplastics in plastic food-
488 contact materials: Release, characterization, pollution level, and influencing factors. *TrAC Trends*
489 *in Analytical Chemistry* 170, 117421. doi:10.1016/j.trac.2023.117421.

490 World Health Organization, 2022. Dietary and inhalation exposure to nano- and microplastic particles
491 and potential implications for human health. WHO, Geneve, 154 pp.
492 <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240054608> (retrieved 21.09.22).

493 Zimmermann, L., Geueke, B., Parkinson, L.V., Schür, C., Wagner, M., Muncke, J., 2025. Food
494 contact articles as source of micro- and nanoplastics: a systematic evidence map. *NPJ science of*
495 *food* 9 (1), 111. doi:10.1038/s41538-025-00470-3.

496 Zimmermann, L., Geueke, B., Durkin, A.M., Devadoss, A., Wagner, M., Muncke, J., 2025. Evidence
497 of microplastics and nanoplastics in food originating from food packaging: protocol for a
498 systematic evidence map. Zenodo; doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7310760.